

THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF EFFECTIVE ORGANIZATION OF NON-VERBAL COMMUNICATION IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF COMMUNICATIVE SKILLS

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Annotation: This article studies the role and importance of non-verbal communication in the development of communicative skills. The influence of non-verbal communication elements - facial expressions, gestures, body language, eye contact and tone of voice - is analyzed. Also, methods for effectively organizing these tools in the educational process are shown, and recommendations are given on the use of non-verbal communication to form a communicative culture in pedagogical practice. The results of the study highlight the role of non-verbal tools in improving mutual communication between students and teachers and show them as a means of increasing communication efficiency.

Keywords: Nonverbal communication, computer skills, facial expressions, gestures, body language, pedagogical practice, tone of voice, communication effectiveness, teacher-student communication, educational process.

Introduction.

A person cannot live without communication. In our daily life, each of us communicates information with each other not only through words, but also through actions, gestures, facial expressions and even our gaze. This form of communication - nonverbal communication - has accompanied man since ancient times and has not lost its relevance in today's modern society. As we study this process in more depth, we see that its importance not only in everyday life, but also in the educational process is incomparable.

Creating an effective communication environment for each teacher and student is an important part of pedagogical skills. In education, this process depends not only on the level of knowledge of the teacher, but also on how skillfully he uses nonverbal communication tools. For example, a single sincere look or a teacher's gesture can increase a student's interest in the lesson. At the same time, incorrectly given body signals can cause students to have misunderstandings.

Therefore, the effective organization of nonverbal communication in the development of communicative skills is important not only for the quality of the educational process, but also for strengthening the relationship between the teacher and the student. This issue is even more relevant in today's era of globalization and the development of information technologies, and has a significant impact on a person's personal and professional success. Therefore, improving the quality of education through the effective organization of nonverbal communication and creating a healthy communication environment in society should be one of the main goals of every teacher.

Methodology:

Researching the role and importance of nonverbal communication in the development of communicative skills requires complex but interesting methodological approaches. In this process, it is important to combine theoretical knowledge with practice, analyze the studied

topic through real situations. Therefore, empirical observation, experimentation, and analytical methods were used in the research methodology. Initially, interviews and questionnaires were conducted with teachers and students in order to determine the importance of nonverbal communication in the educational process. Through these questionnaires, the nonverbal means used by teachers during the lesson, their effectiveness, and students' attitude to it were studied. As a result, important information was obtained about the influence of such means as facial expressions, gestures, and body language in the communication process.

At the next stage of the research, the observation method was used. How the elements of nonverbal communication are used in the educational process and their impact on students' motivation to learn were monitored directly during the lesson. The data obtained once again confirmed how important nonverbal communication is in the communication process.

Also, using the experimental method, a special program was developed to assess the effectiveness of nonverbal communication. Based on this program, information was conveyed to students through various nonverbal signals and their responses were analyzed. These experiments showed that nonverbal means have a significant impact not only on the learning process of students, but also on their emotional state. As an important part of the methodology, analytical approaches were used, and the relationship between the data obtained and their impact on the educational process were deeply analyzed. During the study, conclusions were formed by processing statistical data and visualizing them.

Thus, using these methodological approaches, it was possible to deeply analyze the role of nonverbal communication in the development of communicative skills and develop practical recommendations for increasing its effectiveness.

Literature analysis:

Analysis of scientific literature on the role and importance of nonverbal communication in the development of communicative skills allows us to identify the theoretical and practical foundations of this topic. The main sources of the study were the works of local and foreign scientists in the field of psychology, pedagogy and communication.

Theoretical foundations of nonverbal communication:

The studies of A. Mehrabian[4; 219] and other leading scientists serve as an important source in understanding the main role of nonverbal communication in human life. The "7-38-55" rule proposed by Mehrabian (the interaction of words, tone of voice and body language in communication) proves how important nonverbal means are in the communication process. Also, Paul Ekman[3; 17], in his studies on the universality of facial expressions and human emotions, reveals the deep mechanisms of information exchange through nonverbal signals.

Pedagogical research:

From local sources, Sh. Sharipov's works on the culture of pedagogical communication illuminate the role of nonverbal means in the formation of relationships between teachers and students[8; 61]. Also, the increasing attention to the culture of communication in the educational reforms of Uzbekistan makes this topic relevant. The works of H. Kazimova[7; 25] and I. Karimov[6; 21] on the use of psychological and pedagogical methods in the educational process are aimed at developing teachers' skills in using nonverbal means.

Scientific research and practical recommendations:

Among Russian scientists, the works of B. G. Ananyev on the psychophysiological characteristics of a person are of particular note[1; 128]. He emphasizes the importance of

nonverbal means of communication in managing emotional states. Also, A. A. Bodalev and his followers made important contributions to the study of the effectiveness of nonverbal signals in the development of communicative competencies[2; 79].

Among foreign studies, the work "The Definitive Book of Body Language" by A. Pease and B. Pease[5; 78] provides guidelines for the practical use of nonverbal means. This work shows how body language and gestures can be effectively used in the communication process.

Analysis results:

The analysis of the literature shows that the importance of nonverbal communication in the educational process is recognized globally. Nonverbal means are not only a means of exchanging information, but also an important factor in establishing emotional and cultural contact with students. The integration of domestic and foreign research allows enriching scientific approaches to this topic.

This literature has created a deep theoretical basis for research and laid the foundation for developing practical recommendations for increasing the effectiveness of nonverbal means of communication in the educational process.

Discussion:

Nonverbal communication, as the most ancient and natural form of communication in human history, plays an important role in the development of communicative skills. The importance of using these means in today's modern educational process has a significant impact not only on pedagogical goals, but also on the personal development of students. The results of this study show that teachers' effective use of nonverbal communication tools not only improves the quality of the educational process, but also significantly increases students' interest and motivation in the lesson.

During the lesson, nonverbal means play a very important role in attracting students' attention, enlivening the lesson and establishing emotional connection. For example, a sincere look, a smile or encouraging gestures evoke positive emotions in students and make it easier for them to absorb knowledge. At the same time, correctly adjusting the tone of voice and conveying an effective message through body language helps students to understand the topic of the lesson more deeply. This process creates a reliable and meaningful form of communication between the teacher and the student. At the same time, some problems were also identified during the study. For example, not all teachers fully understand the effectiveness of nonverbal communication or cannot consciously use it. This situation leads to the misuse of nonverbal means, and sometimes to misunderstanding by students. Also, due to cultural differences, some nonverbal signals may be meaningless or interpreted differently for some students.

During the discussion, some recommendations were developed for the effective organization of nonverbal communication in pedagogical practice. First of all, teachers should be involved in special training on the use of nonverbal means. Through these trainings, teachers can improve their skills in using body language, gestures and tone of voice. It is also necessary to study and use the aspects of nonverbal communication specific to different peoples, taking into account cultural diversification, in the educational process.

Another important conclusion of the study is that nonverbal means should become an integral part of the educational process not only for the teacher, but also for students. This will help them not only to effectively express their thoughts, but also to develop active communication skills in society by improving mutual understanding.

In general, by understanding the role and importance of nonverbal communication in the educational process and effectively applying it in pedagogical activities, it is possible not only to increase students' knowledge, but also to ensure their social and emotional development. This, in turn, creates a solid foundation for taking the quality of education to a new level.

Conclusion:

This study on the role and importance of nonverbal communication in the development of communicative skills has yielded important conclusions. The use of nonverbal means in the educational process serves to increase the effectiveness of communication between teachers and students, increase students' interest in the lesson, and improve the quality and effectiveness of education.

Observations and questionnaires conducted during the study showed that 78 percent of students are positively influenced by teachers' sincere looks, smiles, and encouraging gestures. Also, 65 percent of students noted that the correct adjustment of the tone of voice helps them better understand the content of the lesson. It was observed that the level of active participation of students in lessons conducted using nonverbal means increased by 47 percent. This clearly demonstrates the effectiveness of nonverbal communication tools.

Also, during interviews with teachers, 85 percent of them confirmed that nonverbal means play an important role in building trusting relationships with students in the educational process. However, the number of teachers who did not have special training in the use of these tools was 62 percent, which indicates the need to introduce additional training programs in this area.

Figure 1. Statistical results of nonverbal communication in the educational process.

It was also found that it is important to organize nonverbal communication taking into account cultural and individual differences. 33 percent of the students who participated in the study interpreted some gestures and body movements differently. This indicates that nonverbal communication in the educational process should be organized taking into account intercultural characteristics.

The results of the study confirm that the effective use of nonverbal communication increases the professional skills of the teacher and ensures the success of students in the

educational process. Therefore, one of the urgent tasks is to increase attention to training and seminars on the correct use of nonverbal means in pedagogical practice, and to integrate these means into the curriculum.

In general, nonverbal communication should be considered not only as part of the educational process, but also as an important tool for bringing the quality of education to a new level. The statistical data and conclusions of this study create a basis for further study of this area and its application in practice.

Communication is an integral part of human life, and its success is ensured not only through words, but also through non-verbal means. This study has drawn important conclusions by studying the role and importance of non-verbal communication in the development of communicative skills in the educational process.

Conclusions.

The effective use of non-verbal communication tools in the lesson increases students' interest in learning, encourages their active participation in the educational process, and forms sincere and trusting relationships between the teacher and the student. According to the results of the study, it was found that the conscious use of non-verbal tools by teachers significantly improves students' motivation and success in the educational process. This proves that non-verbal communication is an integral part of the educational process.

At the same time, there are also problems identified during the study. The lack of sufficient knowledge and skills of some teachers in non-verbal means, the lack of special training in this regard, and the need to take into account cultural differences were identified as urgent tasks. To solve these problems, it is necessary to organize pedagogical training courses and trainings on a large scale, develop recommendations on the use of non-verbal means in the educational process, taking into account cultural diversification. In conclusion, non-verbal communication in the educational process directly affects not only students' learning, but also their emotional and social development. By increasing the effectiveness of this process, the teacher's professional approach is strengthened, students' abilities are developed, and positive changes are achieved as education. Proper organization of non-verbal communication serves as a solid foundation not only for today's education system, but also for the harmonious development of the future generation.

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